

Customer Feedback on the Five-Star Hotel Industry in Thailand

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This study assessed customers feedback on the Five-star Hotel Industry in Thailand. This study used quantitative research design method of research to determine customers feedback on five-star hotel industry in Thailand and factors that influence customers feedback and a descriptive research design with survey method is applied in the study. The target population is composed of guests of 5 five-star hotels in Bangkok (Marriott Hotel, Oriental Heritage Residence, Novotel Bangkok Sukhumvit, Eastin Grand Hotel, and The Westin Grande Sukhumvit) The total population is 300 persons. The sample size is 300 using quota sampling method (60 guests per hotel). The result of level of factors that influence customers feedback and influences and the level of customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand using SERVQUAL were Strongly Agree. In part of results of comparison on customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand had no significant difference when grouped according to sex, education attainment, and marital status, while customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand had a significant difference when grouped according to age group and income per month at significant level of 0.05. The result of Pearson correlation coefficient between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand and factors that influence customers feedback found that had correlated positive moderate association with customers feedback at significant 0.01 level. The proposed action plan to improve marketing of hotel entrepreneurs and marketer may be discussed during the General Manager meetings of five-star hotel to confirm this research result.

Keywords – Customers feedback, five-star hotel industry, service quality.

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INTRODUCTION

In Thailand, the tourism industry plays an important role in economic and social development of the country because the tourism industry can bring income into the country several hundred billion baht a year. Including the friendliness of the Thai people are all the incentives for foreign tourists to travel to visit Thailand a lot and make a lot of income for Thailand. Therefore, causing the tourism industry such as the hotel business has an expansion rate and there is intense competition to meet the needs of customers to the highest satisfaction and manage operations to meet the set goals.

The hotel business is therefore well-equipped with many amenities to impress the tourists who have visited to want to come back to use the service again. The way to make an impression must consist of many parts whether accommodation rates, location, hotel size, comfort facilities or relaxation areas, including the service of all employees must be of high quality and meet the needs of customers or service providers to maximize satisfaction [1].

The hotel business is an important business in providing food and beverage services and is part of the service industry is the industry that provides facilities and services for travelers and tourists can bring a large amount of foreign currency into Thailand. Due to accommodation, food and beverages. It is necessary for people who are far away from home. Both as a businessman and tourists want comfort and satisfaction as if at home. The decision of the guest depends on many factors such as service rate, accommodation, location, facilities and quality of service etc. Therefore, it can be said that hotel business aside from having tourist attractions which are the main products another thing that can also be a selling point or attraction is the "service" which can be said that the politeness of the tour driver, the caring of the tour guide, the discretion of the hotel receptionist and the attention of the staff. Therefore, operators should adjust the organization's strategy to meet the needs of customers or tourists in order to Mission operations are sustainable [1].

Bangkok is the capital and most populous city of Thailand. Which is the administrative center for education, transportation Finance, banking, commerce, communication, and the prosperity of the country. Located on the Chao Phraya River Delta There is a Chao Phraya river flowing through and dividing the city into 2 sides, the Phra Nakhon side and the Thonburi side. Bangkok has a total area of 1,568.737 sq. Km. with a population of over 6 million. Bangkok is still the 11th tallest skyscraper in the world in the year 2020. The city has many tourist attractions in many forms including religion. Shopping Various shopping centers or night services, such as the Grand Palace, Siam Square, Khao San Road, which attract

a lot of foreign tourists, in the year 2019, Fobs magazine, a business and financial famous in the United States said that Bangkok was ranked as the No. 1 city with foreign tourists in the world with more than 22.78 million tourists and earning more than 2,003 million US dollars from foreign tourists..

Bangkok is a tourist spot. The important tourist attractions include the Grand Palace, Temple of the Emerald Buddha (Wat Phra Kaew), Wat Arun Ratchawaram, Wat Benchamabophit, Dusit Wanaram Ananta Samakhom Throne Hall Bangkok, Art and Culture Center, Silom Road, Siam Square, Madame Tussauds, Bangkok Bank Museum, Asiatique. The Riverfront Magazine Ranking Travel and Leisure Bangkok was chosen as the number one tourist destination in the world in 2008, 2010, 2011 and 2012).

In Bangkok there are the five-star hotels that are popular hotels with tourists and business people like Marriott Hotel, Oriental Heritage Residence, Novotel Bangkok, Amara Bangkok, Eastin Grand Hotel Sathon, The Westin Grand Sukhumvit, Shangri-La Bangkok, Evergreen Place Bangkok, Royal Orchid. Shelaton Hotel and Towers, Chatrium Hotel Riverside Bangkok and Millenium Hilton Bangkok etc.

In addition, quality management is the act of overseeing all activities and tasks that must be accomplished to maintain a desired level of excellence. Focusing on customers means finding and separating what needs, needs and expectations. Client's hopes and then try to meet those needs. It is believed that the long-term success of the company depends on the satisfaction of the customers and the company should focus on making the customers happy. Products and services are designed with that in mind. Things that are considered good or good at one time can be seen as basic needs or needs that are outdated in the next phase to understand the needs, needs and expectations of customers [2].

Customer Feedback is important information for business to define and discuss the importance of listening to customers and having what they value in focus. The voice of the customer (VOC) putting the customer in focus, by collecting information about him/her, analyzing the information and putting them in use for good of the company and the costumer, is described under many different names in quality, marketing and management literature. VOC is a process as a "formal mechanism for soliciting ideas for improvement and innovation from customers", "a mechanism for acquiring, analyzing and utilizing customer driven input to the organizational learning process", and an "absolutely essential element of determining if good customer value is being created and delivered" [2].

The study is beneficial to describe customers' feedback on the five-star Hotel Industry in Thailand for executive of hotels use to important information for develop their policy and services that will allow them to create a competitive advantage. This solution for marketers make use of improved marketing strategies for additional income and other manager such as restaurant manager used to improve quality of foods and present famous Thai food in 4 regions or room service manager improve mini bar in room such as increase snack and many type of soft drink, cashier manager improve process to create fast bill which will impact more on action and strategies to be more effective and efficient of hotel. And there are important data to present good image of hotel for guest used to decision making to reservation five-stars hotel in Thailand.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study assessed customers feedback on the five-star Hotel Industry in Thailand. Specifically, to present the demographic profile of the guest of hotels in terms of sex, age group, educational attainment, marital status and income; to determine the level of factors that influence customers feedback in terms of time of visit, type of room, price paid and other services; to determine the level of customers feedback on the five-star hotel in terms of customers feedback and problems during stay in hotel; Test the significant difference on customers feedback on five-star hotel industry in Thailand when grouped according to profile variables; to test the significant correlation between customers feedback on five-star hotel industry in Thailand and factors that influence customers feedback in terms of time of visit, type of room, other services, and price paid, and to propose action plan to improve quality services that are beyond their competitors and to allow guests to return to use the 5-star hotels in the future and there is important data for guest to decision to reservation hotel in Thailand.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study used quantitative research design method of research to determine customers feedback on five-star hotel industry in Thailand and factors that influence customers feedback and a descriptive research design with survey method is applied in the study. The researcher has used both the primary and the secondary data for the purpose of this study. Secondary data were collected from available books, publications, research studies and websites.

Participants

The target population of the study is composed of guests of 5 five-star hotels in Bangkok (Marriott Hotel,

Oriental Heritage Residence, Novotel Bangkok Sukhumvit, Eastin Grand Hotel, and The Westin Grande Sukhumvit). The total population is 300 persons. The sample size is 300 using quota sampling method (60 guests per hotel).

Data were collected via a survey conducted on guest of 5 five-star hotels in Bangkok -Thailand. A total of 300 questionnaires were distributed out of, which 300 questionnaires were returned and usable for analysis. The number of questionnaires returned represents about 100 percent of the total number of questionnaires distributed.

Data Gathering Instrument

The researcher used quota sampling method in distributing the questionnaire to 5 five-star hotels in Bangkok and sent 60 questionnaires to guest of each five-star hotels. A total of 300 questionnaires sent at cashier counter to give the questionnaire to the guest before checking out using accidental sampling technique. Accidental sampling distributing the questionnaire to 100 guests of 5 five-star hotels in Bangkok -Thailand; Accidental sampling according to Bernardez [3] is a technique whereby chance the samples are included in the study on the basis of their availability at the time the sampling takes place, before its distribution the researcher requested also for the assistance for distribution and retrieval of the survey instrument to guest in five-star hotels in Thailand.

The researcher used self-made questionnaire which was constructed because of literature review and related studies analysis. The instrument has three (3) Parts, Part I dealt with demographic profile of guest; Part II dealt with factors that influence customers feedback in terms of time of visit, type of room, price paid and other services, develop from Sansanee [4]; Part III dealt customers feedback and problems on five-star hotels in Thailand using 5 dimensions of service quality and problems in hotel which the researcher focused the items in a more customer oriented considering customer feedback on five-star hotels in Thailand using service quality 5 dimensions developed by Sansanee [4]. A closed-ended interview-schedule was designed to collect data from guests of five-star hotels in Thailand.

The research instrument collected data was 5-point rating scale questionnaires was used to measure respondents on factor that influence customers feedback of guests of five-star hotel in Thailand and factors that influence customers' feedback. Responses to Part II and Part III were quantitatively measured using an item choice of options was 1 as the lowest and 5 as the highest. The five-point Likert scale was used to measure respondents' perception of guest.

Procedure

The researchers surveyed five-star hotels in Bangkok found that the area along the Chao Phraya River and an important economic area of Bangkok such as silom area were the location of many 5-star hotels, so these areas were used as an area for this research. Then the researcher visited manager of five-star hotels in Bangkok to talk informally for collecting information regarding factor affecting customers feedback and customers feedback and problem in this research.

After collecting all necessary data, It was analyzed and tabulated descriptively. This tabulated information used to measure factors that influence customers feedback on five-star hotel industry in Thailand. The following steps were undertaken in gathering the data to answer the questions in the study. The researcher used accidental sampling in distributing the questionnaire to 100 guests of five-star hotels in Bangkok-Thailand; Accidental sampling according to Bernardez [2] is a technique whereby chance the sampling are included in the study on the basis availability at the time the sampling take place.

Data Analysis

The five-point Likert scale (Likert, 1967) was used to measure respondent’s perceptions of the capability of the entrepreneurs and the problems of entrepreneur with the following assigned values: A 5-point scale has been used which is denoted by 1=Strongly Disagree (SD), 2=Disagree (D), 3=Moderately Agree (MD), 4=Agree (A), and 5=Strongly Agree (SA).

Quantitative data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics: mean, median, standard deviation, frequency, percentage. To measure level of factor the capability of the entrepreneurs and problems of the entrepreneurs. And Inferential Statistics: t-test and One Way ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance.

t-test Independent – This was used to compare of the difference between customers feedback on five-star hotel industry in Thailand when grouped according to sex.

One Way ANOVA – These were used to compare the customer’s feedback on five-star hotel industry in Thailand and grouped according to age group, educational attainment, marital status, and income per month. In case of testing the variance of the variables according to the objectives of the research with the F-test, the test results showed that there was statistically significant difference at least 1 pair at the 0.05 level. A multiple comparison test using the LSD method is required to find a matched pair.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient - These were used to analyst correlation between customer feedback on five-star hotels in Thailand and factors that influence customers’ feedback. Correlation coefficients, r, vary from 0 (no relationship) to 1 (perfect linear relationship) or -1 (perfect

negative linear relationship). Positive coefficients indicate a direct relationship, indicating that as one variable increases, the other variable also increases. Negative correlation coefficients indicate an indirect relationship, indicating that as one variable increases, the other variable decreases.

Cohen’s standard will be used to evaluate the correlation coefficient, where 0.10 to 0.29 represents a weak association between the two variables, 0.30 to 0.49 represents a moderate association, and 0.50 or larger represents a Strongly association

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents’ Profile (N=300)

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	165	55.00
Female	135	45.00
Age group (years)		
Less than 25 year old	18	6.00
25-35 year old	75	25.00
36-45 year old	99	33.00
46-55 year old	93	31.00
Rather than 55 year old	15	5.00
Educational attainment		
Undergraduate Studies	75	25.00
Bachelor Degree	204	68.00
Post-graduate Degree	21	7.00
Marital status		
Single	72	24.00
Married	201	67.00
Widow/Separated	27	9.00
Income per month		
Less than 30,000 baht	-	-
30,001-40,000 baht	69	23.00
40,001-50,000 baht	132	44.00
50,001-60,000 baht	87	29.00
Rather than 60,000 baht	12	4.00

Table 1 presents distribution of respondents’ profile in terms of sex, age group, the educational attainment, marital status and income per month.

Distribution of the respondents by sex shows that there are 165 male respondents (55.00%) while the female respondents are 135 (45.00%). Most of the respondents are male. Distribution of the respondents by age group shows that 99 (33.00%) of them are within 36-45 years old, while 15 (5.00%) of them are the age group of over 55 years old.

Distribution of the respondents by educational attainment shows that 204 (68.00%) of them hold a bachelor’s degree

while 21 (7.00%) of them hold a postgraduate degree. Meanwhile, by marital status shows that 72 (24.00%) of respondents are single 201 (67.00%) of them are married status while 27 (9.00%) them are widow/separated. Distribution of the respondents by income per month shows that, 132 (44.00%) of them are within the income range 40,001-50,000 baht, while 12 (4.00%) of them are within the income range rather than 60,000 baht. Moreover, no one ticked the income range less than 30,000 baht in this research.

Table 2. Summary of Factors that Influence Customers Feedback

	WM	VI	Rank
1. Time of visits	4.72	SA	4
2. Type of room	4.83	SA	1
3. Price paid	4.74	SA	3
4. Other services	4.76	SA	2
Composite Mean	4.76	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50 – 4.49 = Agree (A); 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Agree (MA), 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree (D); 1.00– 1.49 = Strongly disagree (SD)

Table 2 show the summary factors that influence customers feedback regarding time of visit, type of room, price paid and other services. It shows that result has a composite mean of 4.76 with verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Among the factor that influence customers feedback the type of room got the highest mean, 4.83 followed by other services offered (4.76). This result found that most of guest focus on standard room or Small Meeting rooms and Large Conference room on five-star hotel. According to the research in Thailand Sansanee [4] found that guests used five-star hotel for meeting or seminar that use meeting room or conference room because they use more than one meeting rooms in seminars with a large conference while conference room of five-star hotel enough to meet the needs of many members in conference.

According to Department of Tourism [5] described a five-star hotel with a beautiful exterior and interior decoration, complete with amenities and impressive service. The equipment has been maintained in good condition, standard rooms more than 30 square meters with a bed. In addition, there are 3 sets of rooms to choose from. The food room serves both Thai and international dishes. Exercise room with more than 7 species of steam rooms, steam room, jacuzzi room, massage room, swimming pool, meeting room for no less than 4 meeting rooms are available, no less than 4 meeting rooms have safety inspection systems and equipment that modern, environment, landscape, or green area, as appropriate for some hotels.

In terms of other services, this result found that guest focus on restaurant / International buffet /coffee shop because most of the guests love the taste of Thai food and the five-star hotels have an international menu for choose from, such as a buffet, some five-star hotels have a full seafood on ice including King Crab, Crayfish Crayfish, Blue Crab Crabs, Oysters, New Zealand Mussels and Craving Station including Leg Ham, Australian Sirloin Beef, Baked Lamb Legs and Sea

Bass, European food, Foie Gras with Apple Sauce, Baked Beef, Pasta cooked in an open kitchen Homemade thin Dough Pizza and Asian food, Thai food including Indian curry with long flour, Japanese raw fish and Chinese food.

Malin [6] found that when deciding to use business hotel services, it was found that staff were knowledgeable. Understanding of work systems with excellent security. The room has facilities in the room such as TV, refrigerator, internet, and the room decoration is appropriate, can pay the room with a credit card, have staff to advise / offer for sale and reserve a room via the internet there is a fast service. There are other fun facilities such as karaoke rooms is a staff member, dress pictures and looks good, good human relations. The hotel has facilities and other facilities such as swimming pool, fitness center, restaurant, meeting room, banquet hall, etc. The hotel is near the business center, transportation, and travel. And the service is worth the money lost and the hotel is easy to find, with easy access and exiting, parking places that will affect the selection of services.

On the other hand, the price paid (4.74) and time of visit (4.72) got the lowest weighted mean and with strongly agree verbal interpretation. The price paid can be exhibited that guest focus on discount when reservation by Online Booking Providers. Because they can compare price that show list price and room picture and facilities on five-star hotel service in list of online booking provider. The time of visit can be expressed that most of the guests stay or use other service for 1 day. Most of them need to use the meeting or seminars. According to the research in Thailand Sansanee [4] found that most of guests of five-star hotel used five-star hotel for a one-day meeting or seminar.

Table 3. Summary of Customers Feedback on Five-star Hotels in Thailand in terms of SERVQUAL

	WM	VI	Rank
1. Tangible	4.76	SA	5
2. Reliability	4.81	SA	2
3. Responsiveness	4.77	SA	3.5
4. Assurance	4.84	SA	1
5. Empathy	4.77	SA	3.5
Composite Mean	4.79	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA); 3.50 – 4.49 = Agree (A); 2.50 – 3.49 = Moderately Agree (MA), 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree (D); 1.00– 1.49 = Strongly disagree (SD)

Table 3 presents summary of customers feedback on five-star hotels in Thailand in terms of SERVQUAL. As seen in the table, the composite mean of 4.79 and with verbal interpretation of strongly agree. It shows that among the items the assurance (4.84) and reliability (4.81) got the highest weighted mean and with verbal interpretation of strongly agree. Guest focus on assurance and reliability that mean guest need service quality on five-star hotel.

According to Asya [7] state that reliability mean the service firm provides its customers with accurate service the first time without making any mistakes and delivers what it has promised to do by the time that has been agreed upon. In terms

of assurance, it means that employees' behavior will give customers confidence in the firm and that the firm makes customers feel safe. It also means that the employees are always courteous and have the necessary knowledge to respond to customers' questions.

Meanwhile, the responsiveness, empathy (4.77) and tangible (4.76) got the lowest mean. This could be mean that most of the guests of five-star hotel are businesspeople that want luxury and convenience when doing their business.

Empathy means that that the firm understands customers' problems and performs in their best interests as well as giving customers individual personal attention and having convenient operating hour. Responsiveness means that the employees of a service firm are willing to help customers and respond to their requests a well as to inform customers when service will be provided, and then give prompt service. Tangibles is related to the appeal of facilities, equipment and material used by a service firm and to the appearance of service employees [3].

Table 4. Difference of Customers Feedback when grouped according to Sex

Variables		Customers Feedback			df	t	p
		N	Mean	S.D.			
Tangible	Male	165	4.75	.287	298	-.536	.592
	Female	135	4.77	.322			
Reliability	Male	165	4.81	.218	298	-.048	.962
	Female	135	4.81	.259			
Responsiveness	Male	165	4.80	.208	298	2.228	.027*
	Female	135	4.74	.253			
Assurance	Male	165	4.95	.124	298	8.829	.000*
	Female	135	4.71	.287			
Empathy	Male	165	4.68	.349	298	-5.658	.000*
	Female	135	4.87	.247			
Problems during stay	Male	165	4.69	.272	298	.705	.481
	Female	135	4.67	.255			
Customers feedback on Five-star hotel	Male	165	4.76	.184	298	.800	.424
	Female	135	4.74	.195			

*p<0.05 Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 4 presents that Customers feedback on five-star hotels in Thailand had no significant difference between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand when grouped according to sex (t =.800, p=.424, p>0.05), and found that customers feedback on five-star hotels in Thailand had no significant difference between customers feedback on five-star hotel in terms of tangible, reliability, and problems during stay when difference sex at significant

0.05 level. The results of the study determine the gender of guests of a five-star hotel does not affect customers feedback on five-star hotel. Because the guests of five-star hotel need good quality of service to get the best value for their money and fully meet their needs. According to Wasita [8] found that gender does not affect the satisfaction of hotel services.

Table 5. Difference of Customers Feedback when grouped according to Marital Status

Variables	Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	p
Tangible	Between	.150	2	.075	.819	.442
	Within	27.237	297	.092		
Reliability	Between	1.011	2	.505	9.514	.000*
	Within	15.776	297	.053		
Responsiveness	Between	.523	2	.262	5.049	.007*
	Within	15.397	297	.052		
Assurance	Between	3.211	2	1.605	33.013	.000*
	Within	14.443	297	.049		
Empathy	Between	1.316	2	.658	6.585	.002*
	Within	29.684	297	.100		
Problems during stay	Between	.205	2	.103	1.476	.230
	Within	20.657	297	.070		
Customers feedback on five-star hotels	Between	.051	2	.025	.708	.493
	Within	10.599	297	.036		

Table 5 shows result of a difference between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand when grouped according to educational attainment. It is evident that there is no significant difference between educational attainment and customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand (F= .708, p=.493, p>0.05).

However, it was found the there is a significant difference between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand in terms of reliability (F=9.514, p=.000, p<0.05), responsiveness (F=5.049, p=.007, p<0.05), assurance

(F=33.013, p=.000, p<0.05) and empathy (F=6.585, p=.002, p<0.05) at significant 0.05 level.

This is determinant on customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand in terms of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy had difference when difference educational attainment. According to the study of Chonthicha [9] found that personal data which are sex, age, marital status, and income were used in making decision of five-stars hotel service and it was significant at significant 0.05 level.

Table 6. Difference of Customers Feedback when grouped according to Marital Status

Variables	Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	p
Tangible	Between	.378	2	.189	2.078	.127
	Within	27.009	297	.091		
Reliability	Between	.133	2	.066	1.184	.307
	Within	16.654	297	.056		
Responsiveness	Between	1.212	2	.606	12.242	.000*
	Within	14.708	297	.050		
Assurance	Between	1.557	2	.778	14.361	.000*
	Within	16.097	297	.054		
Empathy	Between	2.591	2	1.296	13.544	.000*
	Within	28.409	297	.096		
Problems during stay	Between	.393	2	.196	2.851	.059
	Within	20.469	297	.069		
Customers feedback on five-star hotels	Between	.011	2	.005	.151	.860
	Within	10.639	297	.036		

Table 6 show result of a difference between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand when grouped according to marital status. As seen in table 28 had no significant difference between difference customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand (F=.151, p=.860, p>0.05) when difference marital status and found that had significant between difference customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand in terms of

responsiveness (F=12.242, p=.000, p<0.05), assurance (F=14.361, p=.000, p<0.05) and empathy (F=13.544, p=.000, p<0.05) when difference marital status.

This result determines every guest needs service quality, responsiveness and assurance while staying in hotels. According to the study of Chonthicha [9] found that marital status used to making decision of five-stars hotel service at significant 0.05 level.

Table 7. Correlation between Customers Feedback and Factors that Influence Customers Feedback

Variables	Correlation coefficients					
	(Y)	(X)	(X1)	(X2)	(X3)	(X4)
Customers feedback on five-star hotels in Thailand (Y)	-	.358**	.212*	-.049	.269**	.278**
Factors that influence customers feedback (X)		-	.643**	.201*	.608**	.498**
Time of visit (X1)			-	-.111	.200*	-.026
Type of rooms (X2)				-	-.264*	-.179
Price paid (X3)					-	.314**
Other services (X4)						-

*.Correlation is significant at the =0.05; **.Correlation is significant at the =0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 presents the relationship between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand and factors that influence customers feedback regards to time of visits, type of room, price paid and other services. Moreover, table shows the correlation coefficient between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand and factors that influence customers feedback regards to time of visits, type of rooms, price paid and other services. In this table indicated that there were correlated between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand and factors that influence customers' feedback.

The correlation between the individual factors of factors that influence customers feedback found correlation positive strongly association between factor that influence customers feedback with time of visit ($r=.643$), price paid ($r=.608$), at significant 0.01 level, and there were correlation positive moderate association between factors that influence customers feedback and other services ($r=.498$) at significant

0.01. There was correlation positive weak association between time of visit and price paid ($r=.200$). There was no correlation between time of visit and type of room and other service at significant 0.05 level. There was correlation negative weak association between type of room and price paid ($r=-.264$) at significant 0.05 and there was no correlation between type of room and other service. There was correlation positive moderate association between price paid and other services ($r=.314$) at significant 0.01 level.

It is found out that there were correlate weak association between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand and price paid and other service at significant 0.01 level but there was not correlate between customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand and type of room at significant 0.05. Getting the customer feedback is crucial for the overall success of the hotel continuous improvement as recommended by Briosio and Borbon [10], hotel may form a team or a core group where the task is to generate discussions, solicit feedback, and explain the advertisements on a live virtual platform.

Table 8. Proposed Action Plan to Improve Service Quality of Five-star Hotel Industry in Thailand

Key Result Areas	Strategies	Persons Involved
Tangible	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve the rooms and services for the guests. 2. Recommend other service of hotels to guests. 3. Improve the quality of food served to be competitive to market price. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GM 2. Front Office Staff 3. Front Office Manager
Reliability	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide discounted room price and to attract the attention of guests, 2. Ensure reliable information in social media on services provided 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GM 2. Marketing Department
Responsiveness	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve sale marketing strategy to increase sales and target customers. 3 Improve conference room and meeting room to fit the consumer's segment. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Marketing Department 2. General Managers and Supervisors
Assurance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve hotel information for through social media to understanding right. 2. Use marketing strategies to help improve sale. 3. Enhance the leaflet for recommendation about room and services of hotel to guest. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Marketing Department 2. Social Media Managers
Empathy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. provide feedback form for customers and have staff to solve problems immediately. 2. Organize training plans for employees regarding quality service and paying attention to customers 3. Provide sufficient customer service personnel 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Front and Room Service department 2. HR Department 3. Marketing Department
Marketing factors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improving equipment, tools and equipment for meeting rooms and have enough staff to facilitate the service 2. The price of the meeting room should be revisited when many meeting rooms are rented. 3. There should be special public relations for hotel services. More social media and hotel brochures such as gym, food festival, local product festival etc. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sale Marketing Department 2. Sale Marketing Department 3. Sale Marketing Department/Social Media Manager

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The respondents where entrepreneur in five industry groups consist of manufacturing, service, agriculture and food and construction and real estate businesses. By capital, entrepreneurs Distribution of the respondents by capital are good enough to start

The respondents were guest of five-star hotels industry in Thailand that mostly composed of male, they were relatively age range 36–45-year-old, 33 with married status and hold bachelor's degree certificate and income per month range 40,001-50,001 baht. The result of level of factors that influence customers feedback in terms of time of visit, type of room, and influences and the level of customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand using SERVQUAL in terms of tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy, problems during stay were strongly agree. There is no significant with difference when group to sex, educational attainment, and marital status, while customers feedback on five-star hotels industry in Thailand had significant with age group and income per month at significant level of 0.05. The factors that influence customers feedback found that had correlated positive moderate association with customers feedback at significant 0.01 level. There are correlated positive weak association between customers feedback in terms of time of visit, price paid, and other service at significant 0.01 level and had no correlated between customers feedback in terms of type of room at significant 0.05 level.

For managers of five-star hotel, this may be used as useful for customers feedback that is used for information and the ability to use the framework to identify issues that need to be more important in the development of marketing five-star hotel industry in Thailand. The proposed action plan to improve marketing of hotel entrepreneurs and marketer may be discussed during the General Manager meetings of five-star hotel to confirm this research result. The limitations of this study are important factors for five-star hotel in Bangkok Thailand. This study may be the basis for other research to study other variables for a comprehensive marketing strategy of five-star hotel in other variables.

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